

Spencer York

Independent Researcher

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A Threefold Argument on the Physical Incoherence of Many-Worlds Quantum Mechanics:

Transfinite Cardinality, Cauchy Surfaces, and No Cloning Theorem – Preliminary Draft

Is the many-worlds idea of quantum mechanics flawed? For any given instantaneous moment in time and space, there are infinitely many possible outcomes in infinitely many possible combinations in infinitely many states, thus a three-fold infinite possibility. Then, the immediate next instantaneous moment in time and space, there is the same three-fold infinite possibility, but when considered with the previous time and space moment, the two are multiplied. Thus, from now to the future, the threefold probability increases exponentially, and from time past to now, it has increased exponentially. From all time eternity past and all time eternity future, there is an exponential increase. Now, infinity is just an idea, but some infinities are larger than others, as shown here.

Additionally, these contain the same flaws as General Relativity. The idea of local vs global time and space determinism. We can specify local, but we cannot determine global, because once we do, we can prove that the system does not exist, especially regarding Cauchy surfaces

Also, there's the no-cloning theorem, so branching is not possible, right? Critics may say that the wavefunction doesn't "branch" but rather transforms into an entangled superposition. But if it is an entangled superposition, then this goes back to the insane infinitality I mentioned earlier. The qubits cannot possibly hold that many infinities, right?

Therefore, since the universe is finite, and qubits can only hold a finite amount of information, the universe containing a finite amount of qubits, the many-worlds interpretation is not physically coherent since it requires a transfinite amount of information. A finite world cannot hold a transfinite amount of information.